

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support, Self Efficacy, and Workplace Spirituality on Employee Work Engagement

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Abstract:- The industrial revolution that continues to develop is a separate threat to human resources because the industrial revolution will replace human resources. Eventhough the industrial revolution is a special threat, human resources will still be used as a driving force for the company's vision and mission. Therefore, it is important to conduct this research to determine employee engagement which is influenced by several variables, which are perceived organizational support, self efficacy, and workplace spirituality on work engagement using multiple linear regression analysis. Respondents in this study are 40 employees of CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency. The test results using multiple linear regression state that perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect of 0,026 to work engagement, self efficacy has a positive and significant effect of 0,001 to work engagement, and workplace sipirtuality has a positive and significant effect of 0,000 to work engagement.

Keywords:- Perceived Organizational Support, Self Efficacy, Workplace Spirituality, Work Engagement.

I. INTRODUCTION

The existence of the 4.0 industrial revolution towards a 5.0 society where technology and humans are side by side is a separated threat for every incompetent workforce. The industrial revolution will replace human resources with machine power. Given this, human resources are a determining factor for organizational progress, so it is important for employees to feel attached to their work and are committed to it (work engagement). According to [12] said that to minimize obstacles to achieving company goals, it must be done with the company's driving force. According to the latest Global Workplace report, 85% of employees are found to be disengaged at work [23]. Gallup's latest data now states that in the Global Workplace only 21% of employees are involved in the workplace and 33% of employees thrive on welfare, most of them say they do not find their work meaningful and do not think their life is going well or do not feel there is a hope at work. Based on previous data and

research, if a company gives trust and without pressure at work so that they feel given space to express themselves, these employees will work with enthusiasm because they feel responsible for their work that has been entrusted by the company.

Dwitasari, et al [9] states in his journal that there are two factors that affect work engagement which are external factors and internal factors. The external factor for work engagement is perceived organizational support. When an employee has a positive perceived organizational support, he/she will try to repay it with positive things as well. The company needs to pay attention to how employees perceive in assessing the company's support for them. In addition to external factors, there are also internal factors that is self efficacy which is important for each individual. Self efficacy can encourage employees to complete their work according to goals. The company hopes that each of its employees will have strong self efficacy within themselves because the stronger the self efficacy they have, the more confident they will be in carrying out their work. Not only external factors and internal factors but there is a spiritual that must be instilled in the workplace. Many Workplace Spiritualities are seen as a particular religion or religious tradition. This is because the word spirituality is closely related to the meaning of divinity. At this time the spirituality workplace has a broad discussion not only about religion but can be related to the values of individual harmony with work. Employees who implement workplace spirituality are also influential in work engagement because workplace spirituality is interpreted as an internal condition of a person that encourages the emergence of positive work behavior. In line with the statement of [17] also explained "according to previous theorists, they have recognized that the use of spirituality in the workplace is to increase employee morale, reduce work stress, and burnout."

CV. Elang Indonesia is a company engaged in the procurement of goods and services. The development of the company CV. Elang Indonesia makes the company must provide comfort to employees so that the company's vision and mission are aligned. CV. Elang Indonesia can see the condition of the company, one of which is from the level of

attendance. This level of attendance is one of the attitudes of enthusiasm and enthusiasm of employees at work. Absenteeism according to [19] is the failure of the workforce to be present at the workplace where he/she should have come to work either for medical or other reasons. Linggarwati and Nawawinetu [19] also explained that in general the rate of absenteeism and lost work time due to absenteeism in Indonesia ranges from 3% - 10% whereas if the absentee rate reaches 10% - 15% this is a quite serious situation. The following is the attendance data on the CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency for the period of 2019 to 2021:

Table 1 Attendance Level Report (Permit, Leave, and Sickness) of CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency Period of 2019-2021.

Year	Total Percent Attendance (%)	Total Percent Absenteeism (%)
2019	95	5
2020	92	8
2021	93	7

Source: CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency, 2022
Processed by researchers

Based on attendance data as shown in Table 1, the percentage of employee attendance at CV. Elang Indonesia is quite low. The company sets a critical standard for absenteeism which is set at a maximum of 3%. In 2019, the number of employee attendance is 95% and the number of absences was 5%. In 2020, the number of attendances decreases by 92% and the number of absences increased by 8%. In 2021, it increases by 1% with 93% attendance and 7% absence, so according to the data obtained in Table 1 the engagement of CV Elang Indonesia employees towards employment is still low. The employee attendance rate report for the 2019-2021 period shows a number that is still above the standard value.

The absence of employees at work shows that employees are less enthusiastic about working. Work engagement has several factors that must be considered in improving, that is external factors perceived organizational support in form of the supervisor's lack of assertiveness in reprimanding employees who are not in accordance with the job description. There is also the internal factor which is self efficacy which can be seen from when the company imposes quite difficult work on employees who do not complete it optimally. Apart from internal and external factors, there is a workplace spirituality that every employee must have. It is common knowledge that employees only want wages to work without realizing that at work there must also be a sense of belonging or kinship, so employees will do it sincerely. Those things become the low employees' work engagement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Perceived Organizational Support

The theory explained by Eisenberger in [16] perceived organizational support is the perception of employees that their organization values contribution, cares about well-being, and also fulfills socio-emotional needs. Sun [29] also explains that perceived organizational support shows good treatment

from organizations that create general obligations, based on the norm of reciprocity from employees to care about the organization and treat their organizations well as return.

Sunarto and Suparji [28] explain that employees who hold the perception that their work is valued and cared for by the organization will encourage employees to incorporate membership as members of the organization into their identity. Andani and Wibawa [3] also stated that support from the company will affect the psychology of employees at work, with positive psychological conditions employees will be able to give the best they can to the company. This statement is in line with [10] where the pattern of perceived organizational support is able to direct employees to have an engaged attitude, commitment, job satisfaction to pride in the company so that employees will work with a commitment to goals.

According to [14] perceived organizational support arises from social exchange theory where employees are asked to return favorable treatment and feel an obligation to help the organization achieve its goals when they develop positive beliefs about the organization. Employees who perceive that their organization is supportive will tend to be committed to the organization, which is why it is important for the organization to provide a supportive atmosphere for employees [2].

B. Self Efficacy

Bandura in Hoza, et al [15] defines self efficacy as a person's belief in his ability to exercise some form of control over tasks or actions needed to achieve certain results. Fitriyah, et al [11] explained that self-efficacy consists of self-confidence, self-adaptation ability, cognitive quality and quantity, and acting in stressful conditions.

According to [30] self-efficacy is a belief that arises because one has self-confidence in one's abilities in carrying out a job, so as to be able to obtain success. Noviwati [22] also emphasized that individuals who have high self-efficacy will devote all their effort and attention to achieving goals and failures that occur and make them try even harder. Self efficacy according to Mejia, et al [20] is a person's evaluation of his own ability to organize and carry out a series of actions needed to achieve his performance.

Putri and Frianto [24] describe self-efficacy as the level of confidence of an individual in their ability to carry out and organize actions to achieve the success that is valued from their work. This statement is in line with [22] which states that in difficult situations, people who have low self-efficacy tend to give up easily, while people who have high self-efficacy will try even harder to overcome the challenges that occur.

C. Workplace Spirituality

Workplace Spirituality is defined as a basic human ability to form meaning, values, and beliefs for himself in living life [7]. According to [5] workplace spirituality is essential for the organization, employees who see work as a tool to increase spirituality will try more than employees who see work as earning money.

Baykal [8] explains that workplace spirituality is an important tool needed by modern employees and is very useful for organizations including work engagement. According to [13] the organizational context of workplace spirituality is considered a very potent factor for the organization, especially in terms of retaining employees. Adi and Fithriana [1] explain workplace spirituality is a phenomenon to find a meaningful life and gain deeper self-knowledge to a higher level where individual employees are motivated to find the meaning and purpose of their existence, this awareness is obtained from experience in the work environment or high enthusiasm to complete their tasks to achieve company goals.

D. Work Engagement

Work Engagement according to Maslach and Leiter in a book written by [26] says individuals who have high work engagement are individuals who do not experience emotional exhaustion, or depersonalization, and have high self-efficacy. This opinion is in line [21] who explain work engagement is a business management concept that states that employees who have high engagement are employees who have full involvement and have high work enthusiasm in work and in matters relating to business activities. company in the long run.

According to Schaufeli et al (2012: 71-92) "Engagement is a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption". In this sense, the concept of engagement according to [18] is a positive, emotional and motivational state of mind characterized by enthusiasm, dedication, and absorption. Based on this concept, it can be explained that engagement is a strength that refers to energetic work, being sufficiently ambitious to work hard, even in difficult situations.

Work engagement is important because when it is linked to behavior it will have a positive impact on individuals and organizations, for example when employees show high energy, dedication and enthusiasm, this will equip individuals with the ability to cope with work demands and fatigue which will increase positive achievement. at work [16]. Work engagement according to Fairnandha (2021: 923) is the skills and desire of workers for the prosperity of the company, and their willingness to give a good effort, beyond what is needed to realize the success of the company. Sukoco, et al [27] agree by viewing work engagement as the degree of willingness to unite oneself with work, invest time, ability and energy for work and consider work as part of one's life.

E. Conceptual Framework

Fig 1. Research Conceptual Framework

Based on the explanation above, there are objectives in this study which are as follows:

- To find out and analyze the influence of perceived organizational support, self efficacy, and workplace spirituality partially on the work engagement of the employees of CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency.

F. Previous Research

Table 2 Previous Research

Name	Variables	Results
Christyasari & Lestari (2017)	Perceived organizational support(X1), Self efficacy (X2), Work Engagement (Y)	There is a role for perceived organizational support (POS) and self efficacy in predicting work engagement.
Safariningsih, Rizan, & Handaru	grit(X1), Self Efficacy (X2), Work Engagement (Y)	The results of this study have a positive and significant effect on work engagement
Baykal (2019)	Workplace Spirituality(X), Altruistic Love (Z), and Work Engagement (Y)	Positive relationship between workplace spirituality and work engagement

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

Based on the background in this study, explanatory research is used to explain the relationship between the positions of the variables studied and the influence of other variables. This study uses multiple linear regression analysis.

B. Population and Sample

This study uses a population of the employees of CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency. The samples used are all employees with a total of 40 people. The method used in sampling is saturated sample technique because the population is less than 100.

C. Data Types and Data Sources

The type of data in this study is qualitative data which is quantified and then processed using statistics.

The data sources used in this study are primary data sources obtained from distributing questionnaires and interviews while secondary data sources are obtained from previous research data such as references to journals, books, and websites related to this research topic.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Data Instrument Test

- Reliability Test

Table 3 Reliability Test Results

Research Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Criteria Cronbach's Alpha	Info
Perceived Organizational Support (X1)	0.783	>0.70	Reliable
Self Efficacy (X2)	0.779	>0.70	Reliable
Workplace Spirituality (X3)	0.771	>0.70	Reliable
Work Engagement (Y)	0.768	>0.70	Reliable

Table 3 shows that the results of the Reliability test on the variables perceived organizational support, self efficacy, workplace spirituality, and work engagement are said to be reliable because they have a Cronbach's Alpha value of more than 0.70 which means reliability is acceptable.

B. Data Normality Test

Table 4 Data Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolomogorov-Smirnov Test		
Research variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Unstandardized
N		40
Normal Parameters	Mean	.000000000
	std. Deviation	2.22349264
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.115
	Positive	.115
	Negative	-.105
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.115
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.197

Table 4 normality test results using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. The results of the data normality test show that the value of Asym. Sig. is 0.197. This value is greater than the significance value which is 0.05 so that it can be said that the data in this study are normally distributed.

C. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 5. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Research variable	Regression Coefficient	Sig	Information
Constant	5,883	-	-
Perceived Organizational Support (X1)	0.132	0.026	Significant
Self Efficacy (X2)	0.207	0.001	Significant
Workplace Spirituality (X3)	0.157	0.000	Significant

Based on table 5, it shows that the significant value of the perceived organizational support variable is 0.026 <0.05, the self efficacy variable is 0.001 <0.05, and the work engagement variable is 0.000<0.05.

D. Classic Assumption Test

- Multicollinearity
- Table 6. Multicollinearity Result

Research variable	Collinearity Statistics		Info
	Tolerance	VIF	
Perceived Organizational Support (X1)	0.822	1.217	There is no multicollinearity
Self Efficacy (X2)	0.809	1,236	There is no multicollinearity
Workplace Spirituality (X3)	0.981	1.019	There is no multicollinearity

Table 6 shows that each research variable does not have multicollinearity symptoms. The test results can be seen in the VIF value of perceived organizational support (X1) is 1.217 <10, the VIF self efficacy value (X2) is 1.236 <10, and the VIF workplace spirituality (X3) is 1.019. Based on the test results, it can be said that in this study there is no multicollinearity in all of the independent variables.

- Heteroscedasticity

Fig 2 Heteroscedasticity Results

Based on Figure 2, it shows that there are points that do not resemble a certain pattern and the points spread above and below the number 0, so that it is stated that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model.

E. Hypothesis Test (t test)

The t test is used to test the constants of each independent variable to see whether the variables perceived organizational support (X1), self efficacy (X2), and workplace spirituality (X3) have a partial effect on the dependent variable that is work engagement (Y). The basis for the decision on the t test is to look at the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or significance value. If the value is significant < 0.05 then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, whereas if the value is significant > 0.05 then H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. The t table value in this study was obtained from α ; degree of freedom, $\alpha = 0.05$ degree of freedom two-way test with condition $n-k-1$; $37-3-1 = 33$. So that a value of 2.03452 is obtained as a comparison with the calculated t value. The results of the t test can be seen in the following table:

Table 7 Hypothesis Testing

Research variable	t table	t count	Sig	Info
Perceived Organizational Support (X1)	2.03452	2,338	0.026	H_0 is rejected
Self Efficacy (X2)	2.03452	3,626	0.001	H_0 is rejected
Workplace spirituality (X3)	2.03452	5,464	0.000	H_0 is rejected

Based on Table 7. The t test (Partial Test) shows that all independent variables have a t count $> t_{table}$ with a significance level of $< 5\%$, so that all zero hypotheses or H_0 hypotheses are rejected and the research hypothesis H_a is accepted. This means that the variables perceived organizational support (X1), self efficacy (X2), and workplace spirituality (X3) partially have a significant effect on the work engagement variable (Y). The results of the partially influence between the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) are as follows:

H_0 : Perceived organizational support, self efficacy, and workplace spirituality have no partially significant effect on work engagement on CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency.

H_1 : Perceived organizational support, self efficacy, and workplace spirituality partially have a significant effect on work engagement on CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency.

V. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

There were some research limitations experienced during this research were conducted so that the results of this study may be said to be still not completely accurate and perfect (100%), including the following:

- Researcher cannot fully control the answers of respondents who answered that they were not serious in filling out the statements on the questionnaire.
- Researcher only analyzed the effect of perceived organizational support, self efficacy, and workplace spirituality so that there are other influences that can affect work engagement.
- The population in this study is small and the researcher has not focused on the same (homogeneous) sample.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, the following conclusions can be obtained:

- The results of testing using multiple linear regression of perceived organizational support (X1) have a positive and significant effect of 0.026 partially on work engagement (Y) of CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency, which means that when perceived organizational support increases, work engagement will also increase and vice versa.
- The results of testing using multiple linear regression self efficacy (X2) have a positive and significant effect of 0.001 partially on work engagement (Y) of CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency, which means that when self efficacy increases, work engagement will also increase and vice versa.
- The results of testing using multiple linear regression workplace spirituality (X3) have a positive and significant effect of 0.000 partially on work engagement (Y) of CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency, which means that the Workplace Spirituality increases, so work engagement will also increase and vice versa.

Based on the research results and conclusions in this study, there are several suggestions given for the good of further research, as follows:

- *For Companies (CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency)*
 - CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency is expected to be able to provide positive perceived organizational support for employees so that employees feel cared for in the welfare of the company.
 - CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency is expected to be able to increase employee self efficacy so that employees are more confident in their abilities by knowing that their abilities will maximally carry out the tasks given by the company and the goals of the company will be achieved. In addition, employees will have high work engagement.
 - CV. Elang Indonesia of Jember Regency is expected to be able to increase workplace spirituality in the company. When viewed from the other three variables, this workplace spirituality variable has a positive value that is perceived by employees. Therefore, the company needs to increase it so that employees will be more engaged with their work.
- *For Further Researchers*
 - Future researchers are expected to be able to conduct research on larger companies with larger population numbers so that they can be used as comparisons. Then the next

researcher can add more than three independent variables so that the influence on work engagement is fulfilled, besides that the next researcher is also advised to take a homogeneous research sample or focus the sample on a particular field of work so that the results will be more accurate.

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